
Petroleum Industry and the Nigerian Economy

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Abstract

This study examined the effect of petroleum industry on the Nigerian economy. The time scope of the study covered thirty-four years period which ranged from 1990 to 2023. Nigerian economy (dependent variable) was proxy by Gross Domestic Product while petroleum industry (independent variable) was proxied by petroleum product revenue, petroleum profit tax and refined oil import. The time series data used were sourced from Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletin, World Development Indicator and National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) reports. Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression technique was adopted as the technique of data analysis. The data analysis was facilitated by Econometric views (E-views) statistical package 12.0. The findings of the study revealed that there is a positive and significant relationship between petroleum product revenue and Gross Domestic Product in Nigeria, there is a positive and significant relationship between petroleum profit tax and Gross Domestic Product in Nigeria while there is a negative and significant relationship between refined oil import and Gross Domestic Product in Nigeria. Based on the finding, the study concluded that petroleum industry plays a significant role in driving the growth of the Nigerian economy. It was recommended among others that Nigerian government should intensify its efforts to diversify revenue sources beyond petroleum product revenue and petroleum profit tax. These include investing in sectors such as agriculture, manufacturing, and services to reduce dependence on oil-related income, which is subject to volatile global prices.

Keywords: Gross Domestic Product, Petroleum Industry, Petroleum Product Revenue, Petroleum Profit Tax, Refined Oil Import

1.0 Introduction

The petroleum industry is a pivotal driver of economic activity and development in Nigeria. Since the discovery of crude oil in Oloibiri, Bayelsa State, in 1956, Nigeria has become one of the leading oil producers in Africa and ranks among the top oil-producing countries in the world. The petroleum sector generates the majority of Nigeria's export revenue, a significant portion of government revenue, and supports infrastructure development and public services (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2022). The significance of the petroleum industry to Nigeria's economic structure is underscored by its historical and ongoing contributions to government revenue, employment, and foreign exchange reserves. Nigeria's oil boom in the 1970s transformed its economic landscape, shifting the country from an agrarian economy to a petroleum-dominated one. Today, the oil sector contributes around 90% of export earnings, approximately 60% of government revenue, and about 10% of the nation's GDP (National Bureau of Statistics, 2022). These figures reflect oil's critical role in Nigeria's economy but also highlight the risks associated with over-reliance on a single commodity. Specifically, the petroleum sector has consistently been a major contributor to Nigeria's GDP. According to the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), the oil sector constituted about 10% of Nigeria's GDP as of recent data, which is significantly high compared to other sectors. Despite periodic fluctuations due to global oil price volatility, this sector has provided a stable base for GDP growth in the country, largely through crude oil exports. Oil revenue allows the Nigerian government to fund infrastructural projects, education, healthcare, and other public services, which are essential for economic development (World Bank, 2021). In addition, Appah (2022) stated that petroleum is Nigeria's main export commodity, contributing approximately 90% of total exports. The foreign exchange earned from oil sales enables Nigeria to stabilize its currency and support import needs. According to the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), oil revenues have been a substantial source of foreign exchange reserves, which are critical for maintaining currency stability and fostering trade relations. This reliance, however, also subjects the economy to fluctuations in global oil prices, which can create foreign exchange shortages and affect national reserves. Furthermore, Nwankwo and Ogagarue (2020) noted that the petroleum industry provides direct and indirect employment to millions of Nigerians. Through the oil companies, subcontractors, and supporting industries, the sector creates employment opportunities, particularly in the Niger Delta region, where oil exploration and production activities are concentrated. The industry also facilitates local entrepreneurship by engaging domestic suppliers and contractors for services, thereby stimulating local economies and improving living standards for workers and communities involved.

However, the concentration of economic power in the petroleum sector has crowded out other productive industries, leading to structural imbalances. Before the oil boom, Nigeria had a thriving agricultural sector, which was the mainstay of the economy, employing a majority of the population and contributing significantly to the GDP. However, the discovery of oil led to a gradual neglect of agriculture, manufacturing, and other sectors. This shift contributed to the emergence of the Dutch Disease, whereby high foreign exchange earnings from oil exports led to currency appreciation, making non-oil exports less competitive (Akpan & Atan, 2018). Despite these challenges, the petroleum industry has also enabled Nigeria to make significant strides in infrastructure development. Revenues from oil have funded roads, bridges, schools, hospitals, and other public goods essential for national development. The oil wealth has also supported Nigeria's international engagements, enabling it to play a prominent role in organizations like OPEC, where it has a platform to influence global oil policies.

Statement of the Problem

While the petroleum industry remains a cornerstone of the Nigerian economy, its benefits have been accompanied by significant socio-economic, political, and environmental challenges. One major issue is the economy's vulnerability to oil price fluctuations. Nigeria's dependence on oil exports makes it highly susceptible to global price changes, which can lead to fiscal deficits, currency devaluation, and economic crises when prices fall. The 2014-2016 oil price crash, for example, plunged Nigeria into recession, resulting in a rise in unemployment, inflation, and poverty levels. This recurring problem underscores the need for economic diversification to reduce dependence on oil and to build resilience against external shocks. Another problem associated with the petroleum industry in Nigeria is the environmental degradation it has caused, particularly in the Niger Delta. Oil spills, gas flaring, and other harmful practices have led to widespread pollution of land and water, affecting agriculture and fisheries, which are vital sources of livelihood for local communities. The resulting loss of biodiversity, soil infertility, and contaminated water sources have not only reduced the income of these communities but also posed serious health risks. This ecological damage has provoked resentment among the indigenous communities, who feel marginalized and exploited by both the government and oil companies. Consequently, militancy and vandalism have become common in the region, further disrupting oil production and diminishing the potential economic benefits from the sector. Moreover, the petroleum industry in Nigeria has been plagued by issues of corruption and mismanagement. Despite substantial oil revenues, the Nigerian government has struggled to translate this wealth into widespread development due to misallocation of funds and embezzlement by public officials. Corruption within the oil sector limits the resources available for public spending on essential services like education, healthcare, and infrastructure, exacerbating poverty and inequality across the country. This mismanagement undermines public trust in the government and reduces the effectiveness of the petroleum sector as a driver of sustainable economic growth. Lastly is the "resource curse," a phenomenon whereby countries rich in natural resources, such as oil, experience slower economic growth and higher levels of conflict than resource-poor countries. In Nigeria, the abundance of oil has not led to economic prosperity for all citizens. Instead, it has concentrated wealth in the hands of a few, creating income inequality and social divides. The lack of equitable distribution of oil wealth has exacerbated poverty, especially in rural areas, where many people lack access to basic services and employment opportunities (Sala-i-Martin & Subramanian, 2013). Drawing from the foregoing, this study sought to examine the effect of petroleum industry on the Nigerian economy from 1990 to 2023. Specifically, the study examined the effects of petroleum product revenue, petroleum profit tax and refined oil import on Gross Domestic Product in Nigeria.

2.0 Literature Review

Theoretical Review

Resource Curse Theory

The Resource Curse Theory was initially identified and explored by Richard Auty in 1993. Auty's research focused on the paradox where countries rich in natural resources, particularly non-renewable resources like minerals and oil, often experience lower economic growth and development outcomes compared to resource-poor countries. This observation was counterintuitive, as abundant resources were expected to provide countries with a significant economic advantage. The Resource Curse Theory, sometimes called the "paradox of plenty," suggests that while resource-rich countries gain considerable revenue from their natural assets, they often suffer from poor economic outcomes due to a range of factors, including:

- i. **Economic Over-Reliance:** Many resource-rich countries become overly dependent on their natural resource sector, neglecting other critical sectors like agriculture and manufacturing. This lack of diversification can make their economies highly vulnerable to fluctuations in global resource prices.
- ii. **Governance Challenges:** High resource revenues can lead to corruption, weak governance, and rent-seeking behavior by political elites. This is partly because the influx of easy wealth can reduce the incentive for sound economic planning and investment in public goods like education and infrastructure
- iii. **Political Instability:** Resource wealth can lead to conflicts over control of resources, especially in countries with weak political institutions. This is particularly relevant in countries where resource wealth is concentrated in a specific region or controlled by a small group, creating social and political tensions.
- iv. **Dutch Disease:** A key element of the Resource Curse is the tendency of resource-rich economies to suffer from "Dutch Disease," where a boom in the resource sector leads to currency appreciation, making other exports less competitive and leading to a decline in other economic sectors.

The Resource Curse Theory is relevant to this study. Nigeria's economy illustrates several aspects of Dutch Disease. The country's dependence on oil revenues has led to a relatively strong currency compared to what might be expected from a diversified economy. As a result, non-oil exports such as agriculture and manufacturing have become less competitive internationally. Over the years, Nigeria's agricultural sector, once a significant contributor to GDP, has declined, as has the manufacturing sector, due to reduced incentives for local production (Akpan, 2009). The decline in these sectors has, in turn, limited job creation and increased economic vulnerability, particularly during global oil price declines. Dutch Disease Theory also highlights the challenges associated with revenue volatility in resource-dependent economies. When oil prices are high, Nigeria experiences an influx of revenue and economic expansion. However, when prices fall, as they did in 2014–2016, the country faces recessionary pressures, as other economic sectors are too weak to absorb the shock. This cyclical dependence on oil revenues underscores the need for Nigeria to diversify its economy, a challenge that Dutch Disease theory aptly explains.

Conceptual Review

Nigeria's Petroleum Industry

Oil was first discovered in Nigeria in 1956 at Oloibiri, in present-day Bayelsa State, by Shell-BP. By the early 1970s, oil had become Nigeria's main export, surpassing agriculture, which previously dominated the economy. The creation of the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC) in 1977 solidified government involvement in the industry, enabling greater state control and fostering partnerships with multinational corporations like Shell, Chevron, and ExxonMobil. Since the 1980s, the Nigerian government has reaped substantial revenue from the oil sector, yet fluctuating global oil prices have often created challenges for fiscal stability and economic planning (Udeh, 2020; Obi, 2019). Nigeria's economy heavily depends on oil, which generates more than 80% of government revenues and approximately 95% of its foreign exchange earnings. This dependency has resulted in a "resource curse" phenomenon, where the economy is vulnerable to oil price volatility. High oil prices bring revenue booms, but sudden drops often lead to economic crises, as evidenced during the oil price crashes in 1986 and 2014. Consequently, the Nigerian economy has struggled with diversification, remaining overly reliant on oil and susceptible to shocks in the global energy

market (Akpan & Akpan, 2012; Sala-i-Martin & Subramanian, 2003). In recent years, the Nigerian government has taken steps to reform the petroleum sector, aiming to increase transparency, improve efficiency, and attract investment. The Petroleum Industry Act (PIA) passed in 2021 marks a significant step in this direction. The PIA seeks to create a more stable and transparent regulatory environment, establish a new fiscal framework, and ensure more equitable distribution of oil revenues. However, the success of these reforms will depend on effective implementation and enforcement, which have historically been challenges (Olawuyi, 2021). However, the Nigerian petroleum industry faces several challenges, including corruption, mismanagement, and inefficiencies within the NNPC. Allegations of corruption have marred the industry, with accusations that revenue is misappropriated or mismanaged by both government officials and multinational corporations. These governance issues have prevented the country from fully benefiting from its oil wealth (Omeje, 2006). Moreover, poor infrastructure and outdated refining capacities have led to a situation where Nigeria, despite being a major oil producer, relies on imported refined petroleum products to meet domestic demand. The petroleum industry has had profound environmental impacts, particularly in the Niger Delta region. Oil spills, gas flaring, and pipeline vandalism have degraded farmlands, polluted water sources, and caused significant health problems among local communities. The environmental damage has led to economic losses for locals who rely on fishing and agriculture, fueling social unrest and conflicts within the region. Groups like the Movement for the Emancipation of the Niger Delta (MEND) have protested, sometimes violently, against the exploitation and environmental degradation by oil companies and the government (Eweje, 2006; Watts, 2004).

Petroleum Products and its Composition

Petroleum products are derived from crude oil through refining processes that separate and purify various hydrocarbon fractions. These products, ranging from liquid fuels to heavy oils and solids, serve as crucial sources of energy and raw materials for countless industrial applications. Understanding their composition is essential for optimizing production processes. The composition of petroleum products include:

Gasoline (Petrol): Gasoline is a volatile liquid fuel primarily composed of hydrocarbons with 4 to 12 carbon atoms per molecule. The main components include straight-chain alkanes (e.g., pentane, hexane), branched-chain alkanes (e.g., iso-octane), and aromatic hydrocarbons (e.g., benzene, toluene). Gasoline also contains additives such as octane boosters, anti-knock agents, and detergents to enhance performance and reduce emissions. Its chemical composition determines key properties such as octane rating, vapor pressure, and combustion characteristics, making it suitable for use in spark-ignition engines.

Diesel Fuel: Diesel fuel is a liquid fuel used primarily in compression-ignition engines for vehicles, trucks, and heavy machinery. It is composed of hydrocarbons with carbon chain lengths typically ranging from C10 to C22, including straight-chain alkanes, cycloalkanes, and aromatic compounds. Diesel fuel's chemical composition influences its cetane number, which indicates its ignition quality and combustion characteristics. It contains lower levels of volatile components compared to gasoline, resulting in lower vapor pressure and higher energy density.

Jet Fuel (Aviation Fuel): Jet fuel is a specialized petroleum product used to power aircraft engines. It is typically composed of kerosene-based hydrocarbons, with carbon chain lengths ranging from C8 to C16. Jet fuel must meet stringent specifications regarding volatility, freezing point, and combustion properties to ensure safe and efficient operation of aircraft at

high altitudes and low temperatures. Its chemical composition is optimized to provide high energy density, low viscosity, and excellent cold flow properties.

Heating Oil: Heating oil, also known as fuel oil or kerosene, is a liquid fuel used for residential and commercial heating applications. It is similar in composition to diesel fuel but with a higher proportion of lighter hydrocarbons and lower sulfur content. Heating oil may contain additives to improve flow properties and reduce emissions when burned in heating systems. Its chemical composition affects its combustion efficiency, storage stability, and environmental impact.

Liquefied Petroleum Gas (LPG): Liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) is a mixture of propane and butane gases derived from petroleum refining and natural gas processing. It is commonly used as a fuel for heating, cooking, and vehicle propulsion. LPG is stored under pressure as a liquid but vaporizes into a gaseous state when released from its container. Its composition can vary depending on the source and processing methods used, with propane and butane being the primary components. LPG's chemical composition determines its energy content, vapor pressure, and combustion characteristics.

Heavy Fuel Oil (HFO): Heavy fuel oil is a dense, viscous liquid fuel derived from crude oil refining processes. It contains high molecular weight hydrocarbons, as well as impurities such as sulfur, nitrogen, and heavy metals. Heavy fuel oil is used primarily in marine engines, power plants, and industrial boilers due to its high energy density and relatively low cost compared to lighter petroleum products. Its chemical composition affects its viscosity, combustion properties, and environmental impact, particularly regarding emissions of sulfur dioxide and particulate matter.

Asphalt: Asphalt, also known as bitumen, is a thick, sticky substance derived from crude oil refining or natural deposits. It consists of high molecular weight hydrocarbons and is used primarily in road construction, waterproofing, and roofing applications. Asphalt may contain additives such as polymers and antioxidants to improve its durability and performance in different climates. Its chemical composition influences its viscosity, softening point, and resistance to deformation and aging.

Empirical Literature

Olawuni and Oyeladun (2024) carried out a study on petroleum industry reform in Nigeria: welfare analysis from household budget survey. The data for 5000 households were collected to estimate a demand system for Premium Motor Spirit (PMS), Household Kerosene (HHK), Automotive Gas Oil (AGO). The study found that the reduction or removal of subsidy on Premium Motor Spirit will save largest amount from government budget. When there is distribution concern, the marginal social cost of reducing subsidies on Automotive Gas Oil is lowest supporting the reform that have been carried out by removing subsidies on Automotive Gas Oil. However, marginal social cost for all petroleum products are extremely low suggesting reduction of subsidies on all petroleum products in Nigeria. These findings revealed that equity argument for continue subsidization of household kerosene can no longer be justified since marginal social cost is low. The reality is that apart from the NNPC outlets, there is no other outlet anywhere in Nigeria where kerosene is sold at the subsidised price.

Adebisi, Alenoghena and Charles (2023) investigated the effect of petroleum product prices on Nigeria's manufacturing sector's output between 1981 and 2019. The work employed annual time series data with Autoregressive Distributed Lag Model used for the estimation. The result showed that Petrol and Diesel prices negatively and significantly affect manufacturing output in Nigeria. However, the Gas price showed a positive relationship with

production. Therefore, the study recommends that the refineries that have been comatose be renewed to reduce to the barest minimum the level of importation of petroleum products in Nigeria. Similarly, the power sector should be upgraded to supply the required electricity to these companies to reduce their cost of production and improve their productivity.

Odior and Okoh (2023) examined the issue of pricing policy in the petroleum product sector in Nigeria. The experience over the years has been that of regulation by Government. The study specifically examined the situation critically, and concluded that the solution to the fundamental inefficiency in the petroleum product sector, which manifests in the forms of inappropriate pricing, scarcity of refined petroleum products, smuggling, product adulteration and a situation in which the existing refineries are not maintained on a regular basis, can only be rectified by a well-designed and implemented programme of deregulation.

Appah (2022) investigated the relationship between oil revenue and economic growth in Nigeria. It spanned through the period 1990 through 2019. The specific objectives are to investigate the relationship between crude oil/gas export, petroleum profit tax/royalty, domestic crude oil sales, oil licensing fees on real gross domestic product and real gross national product in Nigeria. And also, ascertain whether the exchange rate moderates the relationship between oil revenue and economic growth in Nigeria. The study employed an ex post facto research design and the secondary data used for the investigation were sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletin, Federal Inland Revenue Service Fact Book and the World Bank Development Website. Descriptive Statistics, Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient and Ordinary Least Square Multiple Regression Statistical tools were used in the study. The results revealed that Crude oil/gas export has a significant and negative relationship with the real gross domestic product in Nigeria; Petroleum profit tax/royalty has a significant and positive relationship with real gross domestic in Nigeria; Domestic crude oil sales have an insignificant and negative relationship with real gross domestic product in Nigeria;

Anthony (2021) examined the effect and causal relationship between petroleum consumption and economic growth in Nigeria during the period of 1980 to 2016. Non autoregressive distribution lag, vector error correction model and causality test were used to determine the effect and causality between petroleum consumption and economic growth of Nigeria. The author found the co-integration and non-linearity between the petroleum products consumption in Nigeria and the economic growth. There was causality between economic growth and the consumption of petroleum products.

Olayungbo and Ojeyinka (2021) studied “the asymmetric response” of Nigerian petroleum product prices to the prices of international crude using data of 1973Q1 to 2020Q2. “Hidden Cointegration approach” was used. The study found that there was an asymmetrical response of the prices of petroleum products to the international prices of crude oil. Positive changes of international crude oil prices resulted to a higher and stronger effect on the prices of petroleum product in Nigeria as compared to the negative changes of the international crude oil prices.

Kabiru and Rabiou (2021) investigated the causal relationship between Nigerian petroleum products prices, exchange rate and inflation during the year 1985 to 2019. Johansen co-integration test, Vector Error Correction and Granger Causality test were used. The study found the existence of strong co-integration between prices of petroleum products in Nigeria and the macroeconomic variables exchange rate and inflation rate. Uni-directional causality existence was found between exchange rate, inflation rate and the prices of petroleum

products. Long-run causality was not existed between inflation rate and the prices of petroleum products in Nigeria.

Mathew and Sunday (2020) examined the effect of Nigerian petroleum products prices on the Nigerian families and the petroleum products prices distributional characteristics. Nigerian living standard measurement survey data of 2010 using data of 53,663 households was used. Quintile analysis was used. The study found that the petroleum product subsidies effect among the Nigerian families do not have “the same distributional welfare impacts”.

Acquah-Andoh, Gyeyir, Aanye and Ifelebuegu (2018) evaluated the sustainability of petroleum production in the light of the medium term policy structure, the Ghana Shared Growth and Development Agenda (GSGDA). In particular, the economic contribution of oil and gas to Ghana’s GDP and sustainable investment options for petroleum revenues were examined using ordinary least squares (OLS) regression. The evidence suggests that at current production levels, petroleum is not a significant contributor to Ghana’s GDP after adjusting for the contribution from other sectors of the economy. The consistent appreciation of Ghana’s real effective exchange rate between 2010 and 2013 led to a deterioration of the competitiveness of the non-oil sector and declining contribution of the agricultural sector to GDP; and further eroded the net impact of petroleum production. Investing petroleum proceeds in the non-oil sector and expansion of the export base are a viable option for utilising petroleum revenues.

Orlu (2017) investigated the effect of premium motor spirit, labor and employment, gross domestic investment, and interest rate on Nigerian economy from 1970 to 2013. Unit root, cointegration test and error correction mechanism were used to analyze the data. The author found that the increment in premium motor spirit price has an impact on the economy of Nigeria and the impact was negative and significant. Gross domestic investment impact relationship was positive and significant. Real gross domestic product, labor employment has a significant and positive impact on real gross domestic product while interest rate relationship impact with gross domestic product was significant and negative.

Otom and Frederick (2016) investigated the relationship between petroleum product price and the job creation in Nigeria using data from 1980 to 2011. Pearson correlation and regression technique were used. The study found that there was a strong relationship between the petroleum product price and the job creation in Nigeria. Variation in job is caused by the petroleum product price changes.

3.0 Methodology

For the purpose of this study, ex-post facto research design was used. Also, secondary data (time series data) were used and these data were mainly sourced from Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletin, World Development Indicator and National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) reports. The data covered a period of 34 years, ranging from 1990 to 2023.

Model Specification

Determining the long run relationship between variables is important as it enables the understanding of the effects they have one against the other. In line with this submission, the model adopted in this study is a multiple regression model. The model is stated functionally, mathematically, econometrically and in log linear form as follows:

Functional Model

The functional form of the model is specified as follows:

$$GDP = f(PPR, PPT, ROI) \tag{3.1}$$

Mathematical Model

Transforming equation (3.1) into mathematical model gives:

$$GDP = \delta_0 + \delta_1(PPR) + \delta_2(PPT) + \delta_3(ROI) \tag{3.2}$$

Econometric Model

Transforming equation (3.2) into econometric model gives:

$$GDP = \delta_0 + \delta_1(PPR) + \delta_2(PPT) + \delta_3(ROI) + U_i \tag{3.3}$$

Log Linear Model

Transforming equation (3.3) into log linear model gives:

$$LOG(GDP) = \delta_0 + \delta_1 LOG(PPR) + \delta_2 LOG(PPT) + \delta_3 LOG(ROI) + U_i \tag{3.4}$$

Where: f = Functional relationship, δ_0 = Constant variable, GDP = Gross Domestic Product, PPR = petroleum product revenue, PPT= petroleum profit tax, ROI= refined oil import, $\delta_1 - \delta_3$ = Parameters of independent variables (proxies of trade openness), U_i = Error term

A Priori Expectation (Economic Theory)

The a priori expectation is used to examine the economic usefulness of the equation with regard to meeting the a priori expected sign of the parameters. The expected nature of relationship among all the variables involved in this study (a priori expectation) is summarized in table 3.1 below:

Table 3.1: Results A Priori Expectation

Variables	Coefficients	Expected Sign	Mathematical Representation
Petroleum product revenue	δ_1	Positive	$\delta_1 > 0$
Petroleum profit tax	δ_2	Positive	$\delta_2 > 0$
Refined oil import	δ_3	Negative	$\delta_3 < 0$

Source: Authors' Idea (2024).

Data Analysis Techniques

Regression analysis aided the determination of the relationship existing between the dependent variable and the independent variables in this study while the data analysis was facilitated by EViews 12.0 statistical package. Additionally, Ordinary Least Square (OLS) technique was employed to estimate the model specified. Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) is a method for estimating the unknown parameters in a linear regression model, with the goal of minimizing the sum of the squares of the differences between the observed responses (values of the variable being predicted) in the given dataset and those predicted by a linear function of a set of explanatory variables.

4.0 Data Analysis and Discussion of Findings

Unit Root Test

This study tested for the presence or absence of unit root using Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) to overcome this undesirable outcome. The results are summarized in the table below:

Table 4.1: Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) Test Results

Variables	ADF Test Statistics	5% Critical Value	Stationarity	Order of Integration
$LOG(GDP)$	-4.621966	-2.954021	Level	I(0)
$LOG(PPR)$	-3.222404	-2.954021	Level	I(0)
$LOG(PPT)$	-3.574887	-2.954021	Level	I(0)
$LOG(ROI)$	-4.632899	-2.954021	Level	I(0)

Source: Researchers' Computation, 2024 (EViews 12.0).

From table 4.1 above, the Mackinnon critical value for rejection of unit root hypotheses indicates that Gross Domestic Product (GDP), petroleum product revenue (PPR), petroleum profit tax (PPT) and refined oil import (ROI) were stationary at levels and as such integrated of order zero, I(0). Given that variables are integrated at order 1(0), Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression technique becomes the most appropriate method.

The results obtained are hereby presented in table 4.2 below:

Table 4.2: Empirical Results of Regression Analysis

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Dependent Variable = LOG(GDP)				
C	0.260373	0.205054	1.269774	0.2139
LOG(PPR)	1.249431	0.567341	2.202256	0.0355
LOG(PPT)	3.053509	0.395282	7.724884	0.0000
LOG(ROI)	-0.831553	0.365646	-2.274203	0.0300

R-squared = 0.886009; Adjusted R-squared = 0.878655; F-statistic = 384.8448; Prob(F-statistic) = 0.000000; Durbin-Watson stat = 1.819417

Source: Researchers' Computation, 2024 (EViews 12.0).

Interpretation of Results

1. Interpretation of the Regression Slopes/ Regression Parameters: Petroleum product Revenue (PPR) and Gross Domestic Product (GDP)

The parameter of petroleum product revenue from the empirical result as shown in Table 4.2 has a positive value (1.249431). This implies that petroleum product revenue positively affects Gross Domestic Product in Nigeria. This further implies that a unit increase in petroleum product revenue will lead to a proportionate increase of 1.249431 units in Gross Domestic Product. Contrarily, a unit decrease in petroleum product revenue will lead to a proportionate decrease of 1.249431 units in Gross Domestic Product.

Petroleum profit tax (PPT) and Gross Domestic Product (GDP)

In furtherance, the parameter of petroleum profit tax from the empirical result as shown in table 4.2 has a positive value (3.053509). This implies that petroleum profit tax positively affects Gross Domestic Product in Nigeria. This further implies that a unit increase in petroleum profit tax will lead to a proportionate increase of 3.053509 units in Gross Domestic Product. Contrarily, a unit decrease in petroleum profit tax will lead to a proportionate decrease of 3.053509 units in Gross Domestic Product.

Refined oil import (ROI) and Gross Domestic Product (GDP)

Finally, the parameter of refined oil import from the empirical result as shown in table 4.2 has a negative value (-0.831553). This implies that refined oil import negatively affects Gross Domestic Product in Nigeria. This further implies that a unit increase in refined oil import will lead to a proportionate decrease of 0.831553 units in Gross Domestic Product. Contrarily, a unit decrease in refined oil import will lead to a proportionate increase of 0.831553 units in Gross Domestic Product.

2. Interpretation of R-Squared (R^2)

From the empirical result as shown in Table 4.2, the R-squared (R^2) value is 0.886009. This value implies that the regression line fits the data well. This also implies that about 89 percent

of the variations in Gross Domestic Product are attributable to petroleum product revenue, petroleum profit tax and refined oil import while the remaining 11 percent variation in Gross Domestic Product are attributable to other variables that were not included in the model (error term).

3. Interpretation of Adjusted R-Squared (Adj R²)

Adjusting further for the coefficient of multiple determination, the adjusted R-squared (Adj R²) value from the empirical result shown in Table 4.2 0.878655. This further confirmed that when R-squared is adjusted, 88 percent of the variations in Gross Domestic Product are attributable to petroleum product revenue, petroleum profit tax and refined oil import while the remaining 12 percent variation in Gross Domestic Product are attributable to other variables that were not included in the model (error term).

4. Analysis of T-Test (Significance of Individual Parameter in the Estimated Model)

The t-test was used to verify the truthfulness of a null hypothesis of each coefficient in the model. In other words, it was used to measure the statistical significance of each parameter in the specified model. This was ascertained at 5% level of significance using [n-k] degree of freedom. The **n** number here is the total numbers of observation [34] while the **k** is the total number of variables [4]. The t-test was carried out under the statement of null hypothesis stated below:

H₀: Individual parameter in the specified model is not statistically significant at 5% level of significance.

Decision Rule: If t-calculated value is greater than t-tabulated value, reject the null hypothesis (H₀) at 5% level of significance. On the other hand, if t-calculated value is less than t-tabulated value, accept the null hypothesis (H₀) at 5% level of significance.

The results of the t-test are present in Table 4.3 below:

Table 4.3: Summary of T-Test

Variables	t-calculated Values	t-tabulated Values	Degree of Freedom	Decision Rule	Conclusion/Decision
LOG(PPR)	2.202256	2.042	30	Reject H ₀	Significant
LOG(PPT)	7.724884			Reject H ₀	Significant
LOG(ROI)	2.274203			Reject H ₀	Significant

Source: Researchers' Computation, 2024 (EViews 12.0).

Table 4.3 presented the summary of t-test in this study. The results in the table revealed that petroleum product revenue (PPR), petroleum profit tax (PPT) and refined oil import (ROI) are individually statistically significant and as a result, their individual contribution to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is significant.

5. Analysis of F-test (Significance of Estimated Model)

The F-test was used to measure the overall significance of the regression model, i.e. whether the explanatory (independent) variables exert joint significant effects on the explained (dependent) variable or not. This was ascertained at 5% level of significance using [n-k] degree of freedom. The **n** number here is the total numbers of observation [34] while the **k** is the total number of variables [4]. The t-test was carried out under the statement of null hypothesis stated below:

H₀: Overall parameters estimated are not statistically significant at 5% level of significance.

Decision Rule: If F-calculated value is greater than t-tabulated value, reject the null hypothesis (H₀) at 5% level of significance. On the other hand, if F-calculated value is less than F-tabulated value, accept the null hypothesis (H₀) at 5% level of significance.

The results of the F-test are present in table 4.4 below:

Table 4.4: Summary of F-Test

Variables	F-calculated Values	F-tabulated Values	Degree of Freedom	Decision Rule	Conclusion/Decision
Overall Significance of the Model	384.8448	2.92	3, 30	Reject H ₀	Significant

Source: *Researchers' Computation, 2024 (EViews 12.0).*

Table 4.4 presented the summary of F-test in this study. The results in the table revealed that petroleum product revenue (PPR), petroleum profit tax (PPT) and refined oil import (ROI) have joint significant effects on Gross Domestic Product (GDP).

Post Estimation Tests

Table 4.5: Diagnostic Tests Results

Test	F-Statistic	Probability	Null Hypothesis	Decision
Serial Correlation LM Test	1.287462	0.3251	H ₀ : No serial correlation	Retain H ₀
Normality Test	1.323190	0.3275	H ₀ : Normal distribution	Retain H ₀
Heteroskedasticity Test	0.52908	0.9322	H ₀ : Homoscedasticity	Retain H ₀
Ramsey RESET test	3.79373	0.0667	H ₀ : Correctly specified	Retain H ₀

Source: *Researchers' Computation, 2024 (EViews 12.0).*

The result of serial correlation LM test showed that there is no evidence of autocorrelation given that Breush Godfrey LM test probability value was greater than 0.05. In furtherance, the result of normality test showed that the error term is normally distributed. In addition, the result of heteroscedasticity test showed that it is absent in the model hence confirmed the assumption of homoscedasticity. Finally, the result of Ramsey RESET test showed that the model was correctly specified while no variable is missing in the model.

In conclusion, diagnostic test results in Table 4.5 provided evidence that all the variables (Gross Domestic Product, petroleum product revenue, petroleum profit tax and refined oil import) in our model conform to the basic assumptions of ordinary least squares estimation.

Discussion of Findings

This section presents the discussion of findings of this study. The positive value of petroleum product revenue from our findings indicates that petroleum product revenue has a positive effect on Gross Domestic Product. Also, the p-value for petroleum product revenue which is less at 5% significant level than 0.05 indicates that petroleum product revenue has significant effect on Gross Domestic Product. This finding therefore indicates that petroleum product revenue has significant positive effect on the growth of the Nigerian economy. This finding is in agreement with the finding of Appah (2022) who established that there is a long run relationship between oil revenue and real gross domestic product in Nigeria. In relation to the above, the positive value of petroleum profit tax from our findings indicates that petroleum profit tax has a positive effect on Gross Domestic Product. Also, the p-value for petroleum profit tax which is less at 5% significant level than 0.05 indicates that petroleum profit tax has

significant impact on Gross Domestic Product. This finding therefore indicates that petroleum profit tax has significant positive effect on the growth of the Nigerian economy. This finding is in agreement with the finding of Olawuni and Oyeladun (2024) which stated that petroleum profit tax is important in driving economic growth in Nigeria. Lastly, the negative value of refined oil import from our findings indicates that refined oil import has a negative effect on Gross Domestic Product. Also, the p-value for refined oil import which is less at 5% significant level than 0.05 indicates that refined oil import has significant effect on Gross Domestic Product. This finding therefore indicates that refined oil import has significant negative effect on the growth of the Nigerian economy. This finding is in agreement with the finding of Odior and Okoh (2023) who confirmed that real refined oil import has a significant effect on the growth of the Nigerian economy.

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

This study has determined the effect of petroleum industry on the Nigerian economy. The finding of the study showed that petroleum product revenue, petroleum profit tax and refined oil import have significant effect on Gross Domestic Product in Nigeria. Based on the finding of this study, it can therefore be concluded that petroleum industry plays a significant role in driving the growth of the Nigerian economy.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are proffered based on the findings of this study:

1. Nigerian government should intensify its efforts to diversify revenue sources beyond petroleum product revenue and petroleum profit tax. This should involve investing in sectors such as agriculture, manufacturing, and services to reduce dependence on oil-related income, which is subject to volatile global prices.
2. Nigeria should implement measures to enhance the efficiency and transparency of petroleum profit tax collection and allocation. Regular audits, digital tax systems, and public accountability measures could improve revenue collection from oil companies and minimize losses due to tax evasion.
3. Government can establish public-private partnerships to build and modernize refineries and create favorable conditions for local investors in the oil and gas sector.

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